

Development and Evaluation of Radio-Based Instructional Material in Araling Panlipunan VI

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Article Details:

Received: 25 April 2026

Revised: 30 April 2026

Accepted: 6 May 2026

Published: 15 May 2026

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Recommended Citation:

Pascual, M. J. G., Agustin, A. A. (2026).
Development and Evaluation of Radio-Based
Instructional Material in Araling Panlipunan VI.
The International Review of Multidisciplinary
Research. 1 (5), 509-517.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20195047>

Index Terms:

ADDIE model, araling panlipunan, instructional
material development, philippine revolution,
radio-based instructional material

Abstract. This research focused on the development and evaluation of a Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) learning material for Araling Panlipunan, specifically for Grade 6 students at San Fernando Integrated School. Utilizing a quantitative-developmental design based on the ADDIE model to create the RBI learning material, the resource was developed based on the least mastered competencies as identified through the First Quarter Examination in addition to topics related to the Philippine Revolution such as Sigaw sa Pugad Lawin, Tejeros Convention and Kasunduan sa Biak-na-Bato. An evaluation tool was created by adapting the DepEd LRMS guidelines and data analysis was completed utilizing mean and t-tests. Overall, results indicated a very satisfactory rating (Mean = 3.76) which indicates that the RBI resource meets instructional and technical requirements. In addition to high ratings being obtained across all domains, scriptwriting conventions (mean = 3.80) and intellectual property rights (mean = 3.79) received the highest ratings, however, technical design (mean = 3.69) received the lowest rating; although it also received a very satisfactory rating. Additionally, a statistically significant difference was observed in the domain of intellectual property rights ($t = 2.973, p = 0.008$) in which Master Teachers provided higher ratings to the RBI resource compared to grade 6 teachers. However, statistically significant differences were not observed in any other domain ($P > .05$). The results indicate that RBI is a viable and curriculum-based instructional alternative in contexts where access to technology is limited.

Introduction

The "Araling Panlipunan" subject (Social Studies), is an essential and significant subject (as an Instructional subject) under Elementary, Open Regular COH, that provides a focus on the study of Philippine history, government, economy, geography and culture. Araling Panlipunan teaches students to develop an understanding of each component of Philippine History through the understanding of, developing a strong national identity, civic responsibility and the use of critical thinking skills. Social Studies is designed to provide all learners with an understanding of their country's past and to develop them into well-informed and active citizens of the nation.

As the foundation of Philippine education, the Araling Panlipunan curriculum protects and produces citizens who are knowledgeable, responsible and actively engaged citizens. The program promotes and develops four core skills: (1) Historical consciousness; (2) Geographical consciousness; (3) Civic competence; and (4) Economic consciousness. These integrative skills assist students in developing a sense of justice and identity as a Global Citizen by actively addressing the challenges facing their communities, the environment, the government, and the economy.

Many students feel that the subject is "boring" or "dull". The subject is referred to as less because the majority of the content taught is either a history of how people create societies (historical events), how people create wealth (economic principles), and how societies create ways to govern themselves (government systems), and how societies function (functioning of societies). Because the material relies heavily on facts and established knowledge, it requires a thorough and precise approach to teaching. This often means educators face the constant challenge of sparking student interest and connecting the content to the learners' own lives and perspectives. (Press Reader, 2017).

According to Turhan (2017), Nigerian primary school pupils have an unfavorable attitude and poor performance in social studies due to a lack of interest in the subject. For example, Nigerian children reported that they have become disenchanted with the subject of social studies because they are tired of hearing about their country's colonization by Britain. Since Nigeria is no longer colonized, the children find that they cannot relate to the subject of social studies and that it is therefore not important or relevant to them. King & He's (2017) claim that this situation represents an unacceptable and imbalanced situation in Nigeria's educational system in particular and Nigeria's development as a country in general. This realization prompted Nigerian authorities to place more emphasis on improving teachers' content knowledge. As such, teachers across the country received various types of teacher development through seminars and workshops in order to assist teachers in providing more helpful and relevant social studies classes to their students.

Students who have listening to radio lessons consistently noted positive feelings about the major areas of education, including: (1) learning objectives, (2) subject areas, (3) instructional requirements (including how to complete assignments), and (4) evaluation processes. The data also support the fact that learning from an audio source was able to help them continue to develop their education despite the difficulties of the pandemic. Ablir (2022).

In light of this information, the purpose of this research study is to develop, validate and implement a Radio-Based Instruction (RBI) program for Araling Panlipunan 6 at San Fernando Integrated School which will facilitate preparation and delivery of structured interactive lesson plans that are created and aligned to much of what is being taught in the 6th grade. The RBI program will provide a cost-effective, alternative method of delivering educational material while attempting to address the deficiencies in the available instructional materials and by creating opportunities for further opportunities of interactive learning.

Research Questions

This study is directed towards the development and evaluation of radio-based instructional material in Araling Panlipunan. Specifically, this study answered the following research questions:

1. What radio-based instructional material was developed to improve historical consciousness, geographical consciousness, civic competence and economic awareness among the Grade VI pupils in San Fernando Integrated School?
2. What is the evaluation of Araling Panlipunan teachers and master teachers on the developed material in terms of intellectual property rights, learning competency, instructional design, presentation and organization, assessment, language, scriptwriting conventions and technical design?
3. Is there a significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed radio-based instructional material in terms of the eight domains?

Assumptions of the Study

The hypothesis pursued in this study was, there is no significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed radio-based instructional material in terms of the eight domains.

Methodology

Research Design

Quantitative research design was applied in this study to develop a base of knowledge and an understanding of the social world. Quantitative research is used by social scientists, including communication researchers, to study phenomena or events that impact people.

Quantitative research focuses on gaining knowledge about a specific demographic or population, known as a sample population. Quantitative research is based on applying scientific methods to collect and analyze data that are observed or measured to answer the research question posed about the sample population (Allen, 2017).

In this study, descriptive research methods were used. Descriptive research methods provide a description of the characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. The descriptive research method that has been utilized to study the learning materials being assessed is based on established criteria with respect to both the content-type of the materials and the level of acceptance of context to the least/Master Competencies identified for the unit on functions through the use of a modified instrument for conducting this evaluation (McCombes, 2019).

Instruments

This study used the Evaluation Tool adopted from the Department of Education (DepEd) Guidelines and Processes of LRMS Assessment and Evaluation. It provides a complete basis for assessing teachers-made learning materials regarding quality and effectiveness. The tool contains indicators for evaluating the content, the format or way in which the material is written/presented, the accuracy of the material, the means used to present the material and whether or not the information is current or has been changed. These criteria establish a way to consistently evaluate the contextualized materials.

Data Gathering Procedure

To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the data collection process, the following steps and activities were undertaken:

The researcher secured the necessary approvals to conduct the study by presenting an endorsement letter from the Dean of College of Education to the Schools Division Office of Nueva Vizcaya. After securing division level clearance, the researcher coordinated with the District Supervisor and the principals of each in Bambang II District to schedule the data collection activities.

The developed RBI is based on the determined Least Mastered Competencies on the test results of Grade VI pupils of Bambang II District. These developed RBI was sent to the respondents as their basis for the evaluation.

The Grade VI teachers and master teachers will be given Evaluation Tools to provide responses to research instruments designed specifically for this study. The instruments will include assessment tools created specifically to collect data that may support a localized learning material alignment with learning competencies. The study aims to produce a comprehensive data set through the participation of teachers in the study as part of the research action and will provide real life classroom evidence to make better informed decisions for future instruction.

Before conducting data collection, the researcher provided teachers who are a part of the study waivers/letters of consent with information regarding the purpose of the research, how it would be conducted and what the possible outcomes would be of their participation.

After securing all required approvals and consents, the researcher conducted the data collection via approved instruments and established timelines/procedures for administration of those instruments; The researcher conducted established data collection procedures by gathering data from both Grade 6 and master teachers.

Following the accomplishment of conducting these types of data collection, the researcher began collecting, analyzing and interpreting data from each of the two major research questions addressed in the study. Data from both research questions was manually organized and synthesized to determine trends, patterns and ideas relevant to the objectives of the research.

Upon completion of data analysis/interpretation, the researcher created a summary document with detailed highlights of important findings, implications and recommendations as a result of conducting the research. In the conduct of the study, ethical considerations were observed in that the researcher followed the standard operating procedure of seeking the permission of concerned school authorities to conduct this study; getting the consent of the respondents to participate in this study; and ensured them that the results of this research are kept in strict confidentiality.

Data Analysis

Statistical treatments were applied to the data in order to promote clarity in the analysis and interpretation of the data. The level of evaluation on the developed contextualized learning material of the respondents was determined using mean and standard deviation. A paired t-test was conducted to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference between the Grade VI teachers and master teachers scores where the level of significance was set at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Figure No. 1. Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

The conceptual paradigm shows the interplay of the variables involved in this study and how these connect to formulate the objectives of the study. It makes use of the input-process-output model to present the data needed for the study and how these can be gathered and the proposed output. First, the study determined the least mastered competencies in Araling Panlipunan Grade VI in Bambang II District and from there this was used to determine the topics for the development of the learning material.

From the identified least mastered competencies the researcher proceeded to the process of developing the learning resources and to the evaluation of these materials in terms of Intellectual Property Rights, Learning Competencies, Instructional Design and Presentation and Organization, Assessment, Accuracy and Timeliness of Information, Language, Scripwriting Conventions and Technical Design. Through the thorough development and evaluation of the learning resources this study is geared towards a developed learning resource for Grade VI learners in Araling Panlipunan.

Results and Discussion

This study's sample population consists of all the Grade VI Araling Panlipunan teachers and master teachers in the Bambang II District for the school year 2025-2026, a total of 20 individuals: including 12 teachers and 8 master teachers. These professionals have a critical role in implementing and developing the curriculum with regard to their learners' needs.

Name of Elementary Schools	Grade VI Teachers	Master Teachers	Total
Almaguer North	2	0	2
Almaguer South	0	1	1
San Antonio North	1	0	1
San Antonio South	1	0	1
Bambang East	1	1	2
Bambang North	2	2	4
Dullao	1	0	1
San Fernando IS	2	1	3
Labni	1	0	1
Mabuslo	0	1	1
Abinganan	1	0	1
Abian	0	1	1
Macate	0	1	1
Total	12	8	20

Table No. 1. Frequency Distribution of Respondents of the Identified schools in Bambang II District

Table 1 provides a frequency distribution of the Grade 6 teachers and master teachers from each of the 13 public elementary schools in the Bambang II District who acted as evaluators.

As reflected in table 1, two (2) school personnel were drawn from Almaguer North ES, 1 in Almaguer South ES, 1 in San Antonio North ES, 1 in San Antonio South ES, 2 in Bambang East ES, 4 in Bambang North CS, 1 in Dullao ES, 3 in San Fernando IS, 1 in Labni ES, 1 in Mabuslo ES, 1 in Abinganan ES, 1 in Abian ES and 1 in Macate ES or a total of 12 Grade 6 teachers and 8 master teachers an overall population of 20 personnel who served as evaluators of the developed learning material.

Evaluation of Araling Panlipunan teachers and master teachers on the developed material in terms of intellectual property rights, learning competency, instructional design, presentation and organization, assessment, language, scriptwriting conventions and technical design

The results shown in Table 2 indicate that the master teachers and grade six teachers gave a rating of Very Satisfactory to the developed instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan using a radio-based technology; both teacher groups rated the criteria equally high (mean=3.76). The evaluation shows that the rating from the two groups of evaluators show very little variation and there is no area of weakness for the materials to be improved upon. As such it would appear the instructional materials were technically proficient as well as pedagogically effective.

Criteria	Grade 6 Teachers	Master Teachers	Overall Mean
Intellectual Property rights	3.67 Very Satisfactory	3.92 Very Satisfactory	3.795 Very Satisfactory
Learning Competencies	3.75 Very Satisfactory	3.75 Very Satisfactory	3.75 Very Satisfactory
Instructional Design and Presentation and Organization	3.75 Very Satisfactory	3.77 Very Satisfactory	3.76 Very Satisfactory
Assessment	3.75 Very Satisfactory	3.81 Very Satisfactory	3.78 Very Satisfactory
Accuracy and Timeliness of Information	3.75 Very Satisfactory	3.79 Very Satisfactory	3.77 Very Satisfactory
Language	3.76 Very Satisfactory	3.74 Very Satisfactory	3.75 Very Satisfactory
Scriptwriting conventions	3.77 Very Satisfactory	3.84 Very Satisfactory	3.805 Very Satisfactory
Technical Design	3.72 Very Satisfactory	3.67 Very Satisfactory	3.695 Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.74 Very Satisfactory	3.78 Very Satisfactory	3.76 Very Satisfactory

Table No. 2. Summary of evaluation of Araling Panlipunan teachers and master teachers on the developed radio-based learning material

The results shown in Table 2 indicate that the master teachers and grade six teachers gave a rating of Very Satisfactory to the developed instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan using a radio-based technology; both teacher groups rated the criteria equally high (mean=3.76). The evaluation shows that the rating from the two groups of evaluators show very little variation and there is no area of weakness for the materials to be improved upon. As such it would appear the instructional materials were technically proficient as well as pedagogically effective.

Intellectual Property Rights with a mean of 3.795. Sources were properly acknowledged, and content was developed ethically, complying with both legal and professional obligations.

Learning Competency with a mean of 3.75. Content was well-aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), ensuring constructive alignment with instructional objectives.

Instructional Design, Presentation & Organization with a mean of 3.76. The lesson was logically and learner-friendly arranged, crucial for radio-based instruction where visual cues are absent.

Assessment Component with a mean of 3.78. Assessment methods were appropriate and aligned, supporting both measurement of learning and formative learning processes.

Timeliness and accuracy: The script received a mean rating of 3.77 for timeliness & accuracy. Current and factual information is important when looking at history and social issues to ensure that your instruction is accurate.

Language criterion: Grade 6 teachers rated the script higher (mean = 3.75) than Master Teachers, which may be attributed to daily interactions with students, and determining that it is suitable, clear, and accessible for their students. In addition, the script accomplished a conversational style appropriate for audio-based learning.

Scriptwriting conventions: The script for radio-based instruction received a mean rating of 3.805 for conforming to scriptwriting conventions and was rated the highest of the four criteria. This shows that the script has been written well, with clear cues, engaging language, and organized segments, in order to keep student engaged, and allow for a sense of presence when in a radio instructional setting.

Technical design: The script received a mean rating of 3.695 for technical design, which was the lowest rating of the four criteria, while still acceptable (Very Satisfactory). Suggested improvements include audio clarity, editing smoothness, and production quality, as technical issues can hinder students' comprehension. However, all materials met acceptable standards.

Both Master Teachers' & Grade VI Teachers' average mean ratings were 3.76, indicating both groups had high levels of satisfaction with the materials, with both groups having agreement related to the quality of the materials.

In the Philippines, radio-based instruction is a viable/accessible alternative method of providing instruction due to technological limitations for the majority of learners in the Philippines; therefore, this study supports further development.

Both master teachers and Grade VI teachers rated the material as suitable for educational purposes at a high level of satisfaction, the Grade 6 teachers were slightly more positive about their overall satisfaction with the material's audio elements than were the master teachers. One reason for this disparity could be the fact that Grade VI teachers have a closer daily interaction with learners and recognize how much the students pay attention to the sound elements used in the instructional materials. Music and sound effects are not only decorative elements in an instructional audio format; when used intentionally, they can signal transitions between sections of content, emphasize important ideas and concepts and help maintain student engagement and motivation. Radio-based instructional materials should include clear and purposeful audio elements to keep learners focused on the content delivery (Department of Education, 2020). The high level of satisfaction reported by both groups of educators indicates that the developed instructional material was consistent with the national guidelines for distance learning.

Difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed radio-based instructional material in terms of the eight factors

The analysis revealed that Master Teachers were significantly more aware than Grade VI Teachers of their rights as creators. This was measured by comparing their scores on an Intellectual Property Rights awareness scale, where Master Teachers scored significantly higher (t-value = 2.973, p-value = 0.008 – $p < 0.05$). Master Teachers are more likely than Grade VI Teachers to be considerate in their use of proper citations, sources of information, and compliance with copyright when creating learning materials. The Philippine Intellectual Property Office emphasizes the need to protect intellectual property in educational resources, supported by the UNESCO statement (2019) that quality learning materials should respect copyright but not prevent responsible use and adaptation. Thus, the difference between the two groups appears to indicate different levels of understanding of the use of policies rather than different perspectives on the quality of the tools.

Criteria	Groupings	Mean	Computed t-value	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Intellectual Property rights	Grade 6 Teachers	3.67	2.973	0.008	Reject Null Hypothesis	Significant
	Master Teachers	3.92				
Learning Competencies	Grade 6 Teachers	3.7500	0.000	1.000	Accept Null Hypothesis	Not Significant
	Master Teachers	3.7500				
Instructional Design and Presentation and Organization	Grade 6 Teachers	3.7500	0.545	0.599	Accept Null Hypothesis	Not Significant
	Master Teachers	3.7692				
Assessment	Grade 6 Teachers	3.7500	0.526	0.605	Accept Null Hypothesis	Not Significant

	Master Teachers		3.8125					
Accuracy and Timeliness of Information	Grade 6 Teachers	6	3.7500	0.513	0.614	Accept Null Hypothesis	Not Significant	
	Master Teachers		3.7917					
Language	Grade 6 Teachers	6	3.7593	0.491	0.629	Accept Null Hypothesis	Not Significant	
	Master Teachers		3.7361					
Scriptwriting conventions	Grade 6 Teachers	6	3.7708	1.239	0.231	Accept Null Hypothesis	Not Significant	
	Master Teachers		3.8438					
Technical Design	Grade 6 Teachers	6	3.7222	0.651	0.523	Accept Null Hypothesis	Not Significant	
	Master Teachers		3.6667					
Overall	Grade 6 Teachers	6	3.7399	1.090	0.290	Accept Hypothesis	Null Not Significant	
	Master Teachers		3.7858					

Table No. 3. Summary of t-test computation on the difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed radio-based learning material

There were no important differences observed across the remaining parts of the evaluation criteria, which included learning competencies, instructional design, presentation and organization, assessment, accuracy and timeliness of information, language, script writing conventions, technical design and overall rating. The groups also had similar means for Learning Competencies (t-value = 0.000, p-value = 1.000), indicating equal levels of linked Learning Competencies among the two groups as related to the Araling Panlipunan curriculum. Achievement in this part is significant, as per the Department of Education's (2016) commitment to a standard-based curriculum as established in the K-12 curriculum, which aims to provide teachers with more confidence by supporting their alignment of materials and appropriate learning competencies.

In addition, there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups with respect to Accuracy of Information, Language Appropriateness and Timeliness. Both groups agreed that the content had been accurate, timely and appropriate for sixth graders.

Araling Panlipunan relies on knowledge of Socio-Cultural, Civic and Historical context while demanding both factual accuracy and relevance for the context of the information. Instructional accuracy fosters critical thinking skills and civic awareness, according to Gitalan (2022). Communicating via language forms the basis for learners primarily involved in audio-based learning because they rely on their listening skills to learn new things. The learners consistently rated the scripts positively; meeting the established standards for radio script writing such as Clarity, Tone and Logical Flow supports this finding.

There is no statistically significant difference between the two groups. Groups agree on quality and effectiveness of the radio-based learning materials; therefore, these materials reflect professional standards across all tiers and sub-domains of education. Radio-based instruction has been adopted globally as a viable and inclusive educational method, especially in areas with limited access to the internet. As noted by the World Bank (2020), radio can be a means of continuing education in environments with very limited resources. Our results support this assertion. Both Master Teachers and Grade VI teachers appeared to recognize the value of the educational product they assisted in developing.

Based on the combined observations, the radio-based learning materials were pedagogically sound, technically sound, aligned with the curriculum and were generally well received by the respective teacher population. The only area where there are discrepancies among teacher populations is with Intellectual Property Rights regarding how to appropriately credit sources or to adhere to copyright regulations. However, based on strong agreement throughout all other areas, this is a positive indicator. It means these materials could work well for Araling Panlipunan, whether used in a classroom or for distance learning.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The Radio Based Instruction (RBI) was developed based on identified learning gaps, using the ADDIE model provided an outline to ensure RBI materials were aligned to curriculum and focused on learner needs. The RBI, which focused on major events of the Philippine Revolution particularly: Sigaw sa Pugad Lawin, Tejeros Convention and Kasunduan sa Biak-na-Bato, directly addressed areas of weakness in student's ability to understand history as well as support their civic knowledge. Teachers' comments supported the fact that RBI materials are practical and applicable, relevant to the classroom, and can be utilized in schools with minimal or no technology available.

The instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan through radio-based instructional materials are instructional effective and technically sound. They were seen by teachers as aligned to the learning competency standards, well-organized and suitable to the learner. It can be inferred from the high ratings for scriptwriting that the process of developing the dialogue and delivery is important for radio instructional development. On the other hand, the lower than average scores for technical design suggest that there could be some improvement in the audio quality and/or production of the instructional materials. Overall, radio-based instruction is an accessible alternative or complement to classroom instruction, particularly in rural/remote areas where access to digital technology is limited.

There are no significant differences between Master Teachers and Grade 6 Teachers regarding their evaluation of the developed radio-based instructional materials in all aspects except one area which is the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). The two groups have a common consensus that the instructional material has been aligned with the learning competencies of the students; the design of the material is good; the content is accurate; the use of language is clear; the technical aspect of the material is appropriate; and, it is generally effective. One area where there was a significant difference found was in relation to the IPR of the material. It appears that Master Teachers were more concerned about properly citing and/or referencing the copyright information of the authors of the instructional material. The radio-based instructional material is deemed as being suitable and conforming to the professional standards for teaching Araling Panlipunan.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank the colleagues and institutions who provided guidance, feedback, and support throughout the conduct of this research and the preparation of this manuscript. Any remaining errors or omissions are the sole responsibility of the authors.

Funding

This research received no external funding from any public, commercial, or not-for-profit funding agency, and no organization provided financial support for the conduct of the study, authorship, or publication of this article.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.